

UTILIZATION OF SUBSTITUTION, AUGMENTATION, MODIFICATION, AND REDEFINITION MODEL FOR BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN TOURISM MANAGEMENT STUDENTS' SPEAKING AND WRITING SKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13335881>

ABSTRACT

The primary purpose of this study was to determine if the SAMR model could assist the students in improving their English proficiency, organization, grammar, fluency, and word choice in terms of speaking and writing skills. This was carried out in a state university at Sta. Cruz, Laguna. The theories of Experiential, Dual Code, and Language acquisition served as the framework for this study. Quasi-experimental research methodology was adopted in this work. Simple random sampling was used to identify Tourism Management students with certain criteria as study respondents. The Cambridge English Proficiency Test, on the other hand, was chosen as the research instrument. The T-test was also utilized in this investigation for independent samples at the .05 level of significance. The pretest and posttest data were statistically analyzed to see whether learners exposed to the SAMR model fared better than those who were not. The posttest revealed that there was a substantial difference in student performance between the control and experimental groups. Moreover, the study produced an action plan titled "WRITE2SPEAK" or Project on Improving Writing and Speaking Skills in the English Language. Project WRITE2SPEAK has included enrichment exercises to help students cope with areas where they were struggling, including organization, grammar, fluency, and word choice

Keywords: *utilization, SAMR model, "WRITE2SPEAK", writing, speaking, English proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

The English language is often considered as an active universal, the world's language. People who learn the English language view it as personal competence. As a result, many people today, particularly students can speak English. Mastering the English language is a vital skill for students to have. Students who master the language improve both their academic and life skills. Once students understand it, they will be well-accepted by society. English is the world's most extensively used language for communication. It is an international language throughout the world. English is one of the foreign languages spoken in the Philippines. It is the most widely taught foreign language, with instruction ranging from elementary school to tertiary level. By learning English, students are expected to absorb and keep up with scientific, technological, and artistic developments. The teaching of English focuses on learners' capacity to master the four macro skills, which pertain to hearing, speaking, reading, and writing.

As it is, the Philippines is recognized as one of the most populous English-speaking nations. After the Philippine-American War concluded in 1902, the American colonial authority established English as the primary language of government, business, and education. English is currently listed in the Philippines' constitution as one of its official languages. It is the principal medium of instruction in schools and the language of commerce, science, technology, government, and international communication. With two-thirds of the population fluent in English, according to Mariñas (2021), the Philippines was also one of the leading ESL destinations. Even though the majority of the Philippine population speaks English fluently, the EF English Proficiency Index (an annual ranking by English level) has shown a progressive decline in recent years. The Philippines was delegated to the group known as TOEIC. Rex Wallen Tan, general manager of Hopkins International Partners, explained that this was concerning given that taxi drivers in Dubai, United Arab Emirates, were expected to have a TOEIC proficiency score of 650 and business process outsourcing agents should have a score of 850 in the metric, while the average English proficiency score of a Philippine college graduate was only 631.4, according to the Test of English for International Communication metrics the overall average score of Filipino IELTS takers was disappointing because many of them were supposedly "educated." This implies that English standards in the Philippines are declining, according to IPD Education's 2021 outcomes.

The Filipino culture eventually assimilated the English language. Despite persistent disagreements about the preferred medium of instruction, the nation has established language regulations. Following bilingualism, President Gloria Macapagal Arroyo established the Executive Order 210. It is intended to increase the use of English as a teaching tool inside the school system. At the tertiary level, terminology is frequently consistent with that found in course descriptions. Due to this, most of the courses are taught by teachers in English. Due to the linguistic switch from Filipino to English to Filipino and English again, students frequently switch between codes. The relevance of language competence in the workplace is emphasized in community and education.

Retnaningsih (2020) stated that online learning, also known as e-learning, is the only means to give education during the COVID-19 pandemic. This includes university-level coursework. Therefore, it seems sensible to conclude that e-learning should be used. To overcome these obstacles, lecturers must adjust to suitable e-learning implementation strategies. To create technology-based learning, the SAMR model was utilized as a guideline. Izza and Rusydiyah (2020) claimed that internet usage encouraged students to learn. Images, movies, and music are used in conjunction with the teachings to raise students' intellectual awareness and foster the development of their thinking skills. Students who access English-related applications on their phones are another advantage. According to Speck (2022), English language learners benefit from the use of technology. Technology is used in various ways, particularly in education. People knew something near them in the past. However, everyone's thinking has been altered by technology. Students may now instantly use cell phones to interact with their friends, family, and teachers.

Tourism is one of the government's considered sources of revenue. Every country in the world plans how to welcome domestic and international visitors, which necessitates enough human resources. A variety of educational institutions have been established around the world to develop skilled labor. In this regard, language was an essential tourist media tool. Tourism students must have strong speaking and writing skills that they can utilize in the workplace. However, students continue to confront a variety of issues when expressing their communication abilities.

In line with this, the researcher determined students' speaking and writing abilities by incorporating technology. The SAMR Model uses computer software to help teachers and students during the teaching-learning process, particularly in speaking and writing activities. The goal of this study was to see if the SAMR model could improve students' speaking and writing abilities. If this suggested technology integration into students' speaking and writing activities are both successful, it would serve as a launchpad for new creative instruction.

Research Questions

1. What is the pretest result of Tourism students in speaking and writing in the control group in English language proficiency in terms of:
 - 1.1 Organization,
 - 1.2 Grammar,
 - 1.3 Fluency, and
 - 1.4 Word Choice?
2. What is the pretest result of Tourism students in speaking and writing in the experimental group in English language proficiency in terms of:
 - 2.1 Organization,
 - 2.2 Grammar,
 - 2.3 Fluency, and
 - 2.4 Word Choice?

3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest results of the control and experimental groups?
 4. What is the posttest result of Tourism students in speaking and writing in the control group in English language proficiency in terms of:
 - 4.1 Organization
 - 4.2 Grammar,
 - 4.3 Fluency, and
 - 4.4 Word Choice?
 5. What is the posttest result of Tourism students in speaking and writing in the experimental group in English language proficiency in terms of:
 - 5.1 Organization,
 - 5.2 Grammar,
 - 5.3 Fluency, and
 - 5.4 Word Choice?
 6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest results of the control and experimental groups?
 7. What action plan may be proposed based on the results of the study?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized the quasi-experimental method, which sought to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable, was deemed to be the most appropriate research design for this study (Thomas, 2020). The researcher thus collected the learners' raw pretest and posttest data. A pair of groups served as the research subjects in this quasi-experimental investigation. The experimental group and learner-respondent control groups received a pretest and a posttest, respectively. After applying the SAMR model technique, the control group was given conventional teaching-learning procedures, or what the learners performed regularly, to see whether there was a substantial change in the experimental group's English ability.

Research Locale

The study was carried out in one of the state universities in Laguna Province. This university provided both senior high school and college education. One of the programs provided by this university was the College of Hospitality Management and Tourism. Due to the large student body of this college, the researcher felt that many students might

benefit from the study. The study was curious to observe if the experiment had any influence on the student's English skills before and after the experiment.

Research Participants

The population was the first-year students at Laguna State Polytechnic University in Sta. Cruz, Laguna, who enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management program during the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year. The BSTM was divided into four (4) sections, with a total of one hundred fifty-five (155) students

Research Instrument

The instrument used in this study was a validated English Proficiency Test from Cambridge. The speaking test was separated into three (3) sections. The first test involved speaking about a visual presentation. The second test involved them expressing their experiences, while the third involved them giving an argumentative statement. The writing test was composed of two (2) sets of questions. The first part pertained to summarizing a particular article and the second part was essay writing.

Data Gathering Procedure

The required data, hypotheses, and related literary works and concentrates all came from books that were borrowed mainly from the library of Laguna College of Business and Arts (LCBA). The study made use of the internet to strengthen the resources through the utilization of Mendeley, Academia, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar. After validating the questionnaire, the following steps were utilized.

Initially, a formal letter was sent to the Dean of the College of Hospitality Management and Tourism requesting their approval that the tourism students might be the subject of this research. The significance of the study, its goals, how to complete the survey, and when to obtain the results were all discussed by the researcher.

Subsequently, a consent letter and a pretest questionnaire were distributed to all BSTM students to determine their English language proficiency. This questionnaire was to measure the level of speaking and writing skills of the students before applying the SAMR model. The survey questionnaire was self-administered by the students. The results were then compared using the ratings from each section. There was no discernible difference between the experimental and control groups' outcomes.

Afterward, the researcher used the SAMR model in the course design, activities, evaluation, and other areas, according to the instructions given to the experimental group in the classroom. The researcher taught and exposed the students to online resources and gave them hands-on training in navigating the Internet, making Google accounts, encoding, uploading, commenting, and sharing documents using Google Docs.

Furthermore, students were instructed to look for grammar checker sites online that would assist them in detecting and rectifying their errors when composing their output.

The following were the steps of intervention using the SAMR model for the experimental group. In writing skills, at the substitution level, the students composed their written outputs through the use of Google Docs. In augmentation, the students shared their output with their partners through the platform for corrections, feedback, or suggestions using its comment feature. In the modification, the students revised their output and then shared the document with their instructor for comments and suggestions. In redefinition, the class created a Facebook page in which they were able to upload their output so that the other classmates or instructors were able to comment if there were things to be improved or changed. In the aspect of speaking, at the substitute level, the researcher provided an activity regarding how to create a vlog using a sample video and PowerPoint presentation. In augmentation, the students used Google Docs to write down their lines or scripts with the use of available online dictionaries and grammar checkers. The students also used Google Drive for multimedia content and shared it with their groupmates and instructors for comments and suggestions. In the modification, the student enhanced their vlog using online platforms that helped to develop the output. In redefinition, the class created a YouTube channel in which they were able to upload their vlog so that the other classmates or instructors could interact through the comment feature.

The control group followed the course syllabus and carried on as usual in the classroom without receiving any treatment or assistance. After using the SAMR model and conventional way of teaching, the two groups took a posttest. This was also the type of test given in their first test.

Finally, the information was gathered online, documented, and tabulated. The statistician was given all of the collected data and conducted statistical analysis on it. To check if there were any differences, their scores were gathered and reassessed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1.1. A. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Organization

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	2	6.67%
Proficient	85 – 89	1	3.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	5	16.67%
Developing	75 – 79	8	26.67%
Beginning	74 and below	14	46.67%
Total		30	100%

It shows that the learners lack sufficient knowledge in arranging concepts. This scenario suggests that the students have not yet been conversant with or skilled in terms of organizing ideas.

That result was nearly identical to the analysis of Asio and Quijano (2023) in their study on English Proficiency and Academic Performance of College Students. With 250 or 99.6%, nearly all of the respondents were in the low level. There was only one or 4% within the average level. No one achieved a high level. The study found that learners' ability to arrange thoughts needed to be developed further.

In addition, Waluyo and Bucol (2021) argued that among the speaking skills included in the exam namely: vocabulary, organization, and grammar. The most challenging aspect to manage is organization. Individuals could not communicate effectively unless they organized their ideas or information in the context.

Table 1.1. B. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Organization

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	3	10.00%
Developing	75 – 79	4	13.33%
Beginning	74 and below	23	76.67%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	70.80	Beginning	

The results show that learners in the control group struggle to write in English. This implies that the students are unable to articulate their thoughts properly. This occurs initially when the learners have not yet been introduced to the concepts.

To back up this claim of Toba and Norr (2019) in their study on current issues of Indonesian EFL students' writing skills: ability, problem, and reason in writing comparison and contrast essays. The content problem was related to challenges in investigating and developing relevant concepts, including object comparison; as a result, the idea of their essay was sometimes unknown. In terms of organization, errors were found in the sentence organization, lack of transition words, inconsistently composed whole-to-whole, similarities-to-differences, and point-by-point structures, the unstated topic sentence for each body paragraph, undeveloped assisting ideas, and repetition idea/words in the concluding paragraph of the essay.

Table 1.2. A Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Grammar

Indicator s	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	2	6.67%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	3	10.00%
Developing	75 – 79	4	13.33%
Beginning	74 and below	21	70.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	72.00	Beginning	

The findings above suggest that learners in the control group struggle with writing. This shows that these students are unable to convey their concepts. It is also possible to conclude that some students' written expression skills require further growth and polish.

In similar study by Betoni and Ulfaika (2020), it was stated that students who received low grammatical scores on their writing tests could be attributed to one factor which was a lack of students' vocabulary, it was easier for them to write anything they wanted to write. However, students who lacked vocabulary struggled to write even when they had ideas.

Table 1.2. B. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Grammar

Indicator s	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	4	13.33%
Developing	75 – 79	6	20.00%
Beginning	74 and below	20	66.67%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	72.07	Beginning	

The college students in the control group have lower levels of proficiency in grammar. This suggests that their knowledge of grammar is inadequate and that they are not familiar with the structure of language manifested in their performance in writing.

Puspitaloka (2019) found out that grammar proficiency was vital in helping a learner understand the meaning of a sentence throughout the writing process. Having a set of grammar skills did not imply that someone can produce descriptive text automatically. Critical thinking must be increased so that she/he can jot down the descriptive text as well. Even if the influence of critical thinking is not as strong as grammatical mastery, it was an inner modality for a learner to take an advanced activity to write properly.

Table 1.3. A Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Fluency

Indicator s	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	1	3.33%
Proficient	85 – 89	1	3.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	6	20.00%
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	22	73.33%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	72.33	Beginning	

The factors causing speaking problems are lack of general knowledge, lack of speaking practice, fear of making mistakes, lack of word usage and grammar practice, poor motivation, low involvement, reading laziness, shyness, less dictionary usage, anxiousness, fear of criticism, and unfamiliar word pronunciation are all contributing factors to speaking difficulties.

Based on the study, the aspects of fluency across assessed levels of speaking proficiency by Tavakoli et al. (2020). Students still felt guilt and anxiety during dialogues. This was a critical component in encouraging students to refrain from speaking in public. This was due to a lack of self-confidence, and learners' vocabulary was relatively low. Therefore, they preferred quiet over talking or having a discourse.

Table 1.3. B. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	3	10.00%
Developing	75 – 79	4	13.33%
Beginning	74 and below	23	76.67%
Total		30	100%

Learners have difficulties when it comes to writing. These problems can be caused by a variety of factors like lack of practice, insufficient time, a lack of enthusiasm, feedback from the instructor, and the nature of the writing process.

To back up this, The Role of Handwriting Instruction in Education by Limpo and Graham (2020) found that good and fluent handwriting was required for efficient and effective writing development, which could be promoted by explicit and systematic training.

Table 1.4. A. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Word Choice

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	2	6.67%
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	3	10.00%
Developing	75 – 79	7	23.33%
Beginning	74 and below	18	60.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	73.80	Beginning	

Communication challenges arise when the learner encounters a word. They do not comprehend, use a word they are unfamiliar with, or are unable to articulate their intended meaning. Other issues that students face when speaking include a lack of self-confidence and anxiousness. They may experience sentiments such as insecurity, shyness, anxiety, nervousness, and worry that interfere with their speaking abilities. If the learners themselves do not believe that they can speak, it has become a major issue for them.

Aziz and Kashinathan (2021) found that few difficulties with communication were reported among college students. The students believed they could not compose English sentences because of their restricted terminology. Furthermore, learners took far too long to produce English phrases. They began with words and strived to organize the complete language into sentences and phrases before conversing. They also employed erroneous phrase structure and pronunciation frequently.

Table 1.4. B. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Word Choice

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0

Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	1	3.33%
Developing	75 – 79	5	16.67%
Beginning	74 and below	24	80.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	71.60	Beginning	

Many of the students who do not read much or come across a diverse range of vocabulary in their daily life may have a restricted word bank to draw on. This makes it tough to choose the most exact and striking phrases to explain their ideas.

According to Derakhshan and Karimian Shirejini (2020), punctuation, the use of prepositions, weak expressions, exceptional structure, consistency, and the use of irregular verbs, all played important roles in making writing difficult. This could be considered an intrinsic aspect of the English learning process; therefore, understanding the learners' academic writing challenges and their attitudes about such problematic regions was critical in the educational context. Students were faced with developing logical writing in addition to correct sentence construction and paragraph development.

Table 2.1. A. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Organization

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	11	36.67%
Developing	75 – 79	7	23.33%
Beginning	74 and below	12	40.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	76.40	Developing	

The experimental group experienced problems in speaking skills regarding organization, based on their overall score. It simply indicates that the students are unable to arrange the ideas in a particular context.

According to Islam and Stapa (2021), learners were also hampered by a lack of previous knowledge on a variety of topics. They appeared to struggle to retrieve material from their long-term memory when they attempted to speak on a topic. Having appropriate topical knowledge enabled speakers to connect to the context, and with this connection, they might continue a conversation or build a speech. It was believed that learners' speaking performance was substantially influenced by how much knowledge and thoughts they had about the issue at hand.

Table 2.1. B. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Organization

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	2	6.67%
Developing	75 – 79	4	13.33%
Beginning	74 and below	24	80.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	69.67	Beginning	

College students show deficiency when it comes to establishing ideas and information in writing activities despite having a series of tests, training, and learning from the past.

To support this, Siddiqui (2020) found that writing in English is extremely important all around the world, especially for academic and professional success. Despite having studied English for years, tertiary students, like other foreign language students, struggled with writing. One of the primary challenges in their writing was unable to express or organize their thoughts in a paragraph to convey the proper sense.

Table 2.2. A. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Grammar

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	5	16.67%
Developing	75 – 79	6	20.00%
Beginning	74 and below	19	63.33%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	73.00	Beginning	

The Tourism students in the experimental group perform poorly in grammar. This suggests a lack of grammatical competence and a lack of familiarity with a grammar structure.

According to Wahyuningsih and Afandi (2020), the analysis results showed that the problems encountered by students in the English language education department in speaking English included a lack of appropriate vocabulary, a lack of grammar mastery,

a lack of correct pronunciation, a lack of English input outside of the classroom, a lack of confidence, and a lack of English-speaking curriculum development.

Table 2.2. B. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Grammar

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	1	3.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	3	10.00%
Developing	75 – 79	5	16.67%
Beginning	74 and below	21	70.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	70.53	Beginning	

The findings indicate that learners' grammar competency in writing is low. This occurs when a learner does not understand what he or she is reading and does not have a strong command of the vocabulary.

According to Omar (2019), many English language learners have been facing difficulties when writing an academic paper in English due to a lack of grammar. Most foreign colleges required passing international tests at a high level, which most international students have failed to do. The cause was attributed to a lack of fundamental knowledge about grammar in writing.

Table 2.3. A. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	2	6.67%
Developing	75 – 79	10	33.33%
Beginning	74 and below	18	60.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	72.67	Beginning	

This only connotes that the students have poor communication skills, this happens when learners are not encouraged to express their ideas, thoughts, and feelings inside or outside of the classrooms. As a result, the students become more unwilling and experience stage fright or lack of self-confidence in using English as a language.

Some may have attributed this shortcoming to a lack of time for oral practice both in and out of the classroom (Su, 2021). As a result, students lacked confidence and were unwilling to speak English. They were nervous when they used English to express themselves verbally, had debates, or communicated with teachers or classmates. Furthermore, the bulk of these pupils were not at ease speaking English and were hence not fluent. Some students performed well in English lessons but struggled to communicate in real-life settings.

Additionally, Masuram and Sripada (2020) stated that college students' speaking ability and oral fluency must be evaluated. The majority of learners were having difficulty continuing a discussion with minimal hesitations and unnecessary pauses. There could be a variety of explanations for such occurrences. There could be pedagogical reasons to blame for students' weak public speaking skills.

Table 2.3. B. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	1	3.33%
Developing	75 – 79	6	20.00%
Beginning	74 and below	23	76.67%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	68.80	Beginning	

The findings show that the learners are terrified of making mistakes while writing. When they find it difficult to express themselves in English, they choose to use their own words instead. Limited vocabulary hinders learners' ability to communicate effectively in English.

Ramamuthie and Aziz (2022) stated that English could be difficult for English language learners, especially if they were not exposed to the language well. The most common issue for learners was a lack of confidence in the English language. Participation of students in writing activities necessitated a certain level of interest on their behalf. In general, intrinsic and extrinsic elements that developed the yearning and energy in students to be continually engaged and dedicated to studying and engaging in English activities were characterized as intrinsic and extrinsic components.

Table 2.4. A. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Word Choice

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	8	26.67%
Developing	75 – 79	6	20.00%
Beginning	74 and below	16	53.33%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	74.87	Developing	

The findings show that students demonstrate fear during speaking activities resulting in their struggle in performance. Providing learners with a comfortable setting and a series of activities for them to be exposed to the language was vital for their success. Some learners may struggle to communicate in the language due to their shy type nature or personality.

Syafiq et al. (2021) stated that learners with limited vocabulary and practice might struggle to communicate effectively in English. Lack of material could cause anxiety and impair communication skills. In the event the learners might be fearful of making mistakes or being ridiculed by their peers, preventing them from sharing their thoughts.

Table 2.4. B. Pretest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Word Choice

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	1	3.33%
Developing	75 – 79	2	6.67%
Beginning	74 and below	27	90.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	69.07	Beginning	

There are still fundamental problems in student's writing-related language use, such as organization, tense, quantity, word fragments, deletion, and meaning confusion or ambiguity.

To support this, Mandasari (2019) discovered that the inaccuracies written by students caused confusion and misconception among readers. One hundred-eighty (180) pieces of writing were collected and evaluated from 24 students enrolled in the Business

Correspondence course. The results suggested that word choice was one of the most committed errors, accounting for 9.1% of all errors.

Table 3.1. Test of Significant Difference between the English Language Proficiency Pretest Scores in Speaking of Tourism Students in Control and the Experimental Group

Pretest	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	P value		
Organization	-.09333	1.02619	-.498	.622	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Grammar	-.1000	.99343	-.551	.586	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Fluency	-.0333	.83721	-.218	.829	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Word Choice	-.10667	.90931	-.643	.526	Not Significant	Accept Ho

It signifies that the control and experimental groups performed equally at the start of the investigation. Their pretest results are identical. The pretest results show no statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups, indicating that they were all at or near the same level of English language competence before the study's creation and implementation.

In this sense, students were frequently given a pretest at the start of a course. According to Papageorgiou et al. (2021), this was to determine their baseline understanding of the measurements specified in the learning objectives. It was given before a course to establish a baseline of knowledge.

Table 3.2. Test of Significant Difference between the English Language Proficiency Pretest Scores in Speaking of Tourism Students in Control and the Experimental Group

Pretest	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	P value		
Organization	.1133 3	.8249 3	.752	.458	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Grammar	.1533 3	.8480 1	.990	.330	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Fluency	.0666 7	.7284 1	.501	.620	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Word Choice	.2533	.5655	2.454	.020	Significant	Reject Ho

It means that both the control and experimental groups started the study with the same performance. Their pre-test findings show no differences except in word choice. The pretest findings for the experimental and control groups revealed no statistically significant differences in terms of organization, grammar, and fluency. In contrast, there is a significant difference in terms of word choice.

Zohrabi and Tahmasebi (2020) stated that in his study the result of pretest in both was no statistically significant difference between the experimental and control group regarding grammar, and vocabulary scores. It indicated that both groups have nearly the same competencies before the experiment.

Table 4.1. A. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Organization

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	2	6.67%
Proficient	85 – 89	1	3.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	7	23.33%
Developing	75 – 79	9	30.00%
Beginning	74 and below	11	36.67%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	78.07	Developing	

This table shows that speaking in English in terms of organization can be tough, especially if they do not have good training on how to use the language properly.

Another difficulty that learners confront when learning to speak English is interruption from their mother tongue. According to Budiharto (2019), the students' interlingual errors were classified into four types: grammar errors (words or sentences that are relative to tense, subject-verb agreement, singular/plural markers, articles, and prepositions), lexico-semantic errors (errors associated with incorrect vocabulary meaning), mechanical errors (spelling errors), and word order errors.

Table 4.1. B. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Organization

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	1	3.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	3	10.00%
Developing	75 – 79	5	16.67%

Beginning	74 and below	21	70.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	74.40	Beginning	

The results show that the students do not have a proper guide on how to construct a concise and well-constructed paragraph from their point of view.

To support this, according to Farhan et al. (2019), writing was effective when the message was easy to follow and grasp due to its structure and organization. Language learners must use all paragraph criteria for producing a good paragraph while writing a paragraph to guarantee the message was apparent to the readers. A paragraph was a collection of sentences connected in a succession to build an idea. These ideas were made explicit in paragraphs by descriptions that clearly explained the point of view.

Table 4.2. A. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Grammar

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	3	10.00%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	5	16.67%
Developing	75 – 79	8	26.67%
Beginning	74 and below	14	46.67%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	76.20	Developing	

In terms of grammar, the learners in the control group showed a bit of improvement in their performance on the pretest and posttest. On the other hand, it indicates that the learners have not yet acquired or become acquainted with the grammar structure. This means that the teacher will still need to devise a strategy to improve the performance of their students.

As evidenced by Eisenberg (2020) the primary goal of all grammatical interventions should be to assist students in developing greater facility with syntax and morphology, narration, exposition, and other textual genres in both written and oral modalities. As a result, considering that no additional procedure or intervention was used in the control group, as opposed to the experimental group, it was plausible to conclude that the increase in posttest score in the control group was not significant.

Table 4.1. B. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Grammar

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	6	20.00%
Developing	75 – 79	9	30.00%
Beginning	74 and below	15	50.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	75.40	Developing	

The result indicates that there is a bit of improvement in their performance in writing in terms of grammar. It implies that learners who belonged to the control group are still struggling with written expression. They still cannot articulate cohesive thoughts.

According to Fitria (2021) grammar websites enable students to teach themselves by providing different representations of an idea. Many prominent grammar software products included grammar check online, free grammar checker, online editor, Grammarly, and so on. As for how to check English grammar utilizing the following tools, an internet connection was required, and some of these online grammar check services provided customers with two service options: free or premium features.

Table 4.3. A. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	2	6.67%
Proficient	85 – 89	1	3.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	6	20.00%
Developing	75 – 79	6	20.00%
Beginning	74 and below	15	50.00%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	76.60	Developing	

The result indicates that there is a bit of improvement in their performance in speaking in terms of fluency. Task-based teaching should be emphasized to promote an engaging activity to enhance their skills in speaking.

Namaziandost, Homayouni, & Rahmani (2020) indicated that improving learners' oral proficiency necessitates primarily overcoming personal obstacles. As a result, teachers must equip learners with a means for increasing their opportunities to utilize

language. Organizing the lesson in groups was one of the best strategies to give learners comprehensive oral production and conversation.

Table 4.3. B. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	7	23.33%
Developing	75 – 79	4	13.33%
Beginning	74 and below	19	63.33%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	74.80	Developing	

To enhance student's fluency in writing, collaborative or cooperative learning should be utilized. It is usually regarded as an important exercise for tertiary students.

To back this up, Pham (2021) found that collaborative writing had a significant impact on students' writing fluency in both cooperatively and separately produced papers. In addition, the study developed an effective framework for collaborative writing activities.

Table 4.4. A. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Word Choice

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	1	3.33%
Proficient	85 – 89	2	6.67%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	6	20.00%
Developing	75 – 79	4	13.33%
Beginning	74 and below	17	56.67%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	76.20	Developing	

As a result, some students may be unable to communicate effectively. As a result, the data strongly suggests that learners require a considerable amount of reading material to improve their speaking skills in terms of pronunciation, vocabulary, and word choice.

In support of this, according to Ambarwati and Mandasari (2020), in terms of pronunciation mastery and vocabulary enrichment, dictionaries had an impact on student

pronunciation and vocabulary. It was proposed that the use of the online Cambridge dictionary as an alternative solution to the pronunciation and word choice.

Table 4.4. B. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Control Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Word Choice

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	0	0
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	4	13.33%
Developing	75 – 79	7	23.33%
Beginning	74 and below	19	63.33%
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	74.40	Beginning	

It shows that instructors should strengthen writing practices in the classroom to improve their students' writing skills. Writing is incredibly useful, even if the writing process remains challenging.

In this regard, the findings of Mantra, Handayani, and Widiastuti's (2021) study revealed that a substantial number of students were still unable to write descriptive paragraphs. Students should, therefore, attend intense writing workshops to strengthen their writing skills.

Table 5.1. A. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Organization

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	15	50.00%
Proficient	85 – 89	7	23.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	7	23.33%
Developing	75 – 79	1	3.33%
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	88.06	Proficient	

As for the outcomes, this means that the students show growth in their speaking activities in terms of organization, they also find ways to engage in classroom activities and become more fun in utilizing technology. They know how to manage conflicts or challenges that they meet in their courses.

Based on the study of Mandasari and Aminatun (2020), it was possible to conclude that video blogging was useful in developing students' speaking abilities. There were several stages that students took when utilizing Vlog in English study. Throughout those stages, students discovered that Vlog provided some benefits for students studying English. Furthermore, students broadened their understanding of the structure of their ideas.

Table 5.1. B. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Organization

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	8	26.67%
Proficient	85 – 89	10	33.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	12	40.00%
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	86.07	Proficient	

The results show that the writing performance of the students has improved in terms of organization. It may be determined that the learners in this group are no longer struggling to organize their ideas in a specific context and can already explain cohesive thoughts. It means that the SAMR model used by the teacher in class aided the pupils in enhancing their writing skills.

According to Williams and Beam (2019), technology-mediated writing instruction yielded improvements in students' composing processes and writing skills as well as their knowledge and use of new literacies. Students designed, produced and presented a variety of multimodal and digital texts that represented their knowledge and understanding of literary material and contemporary social justice issues.

Table 5.2. A. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Grammar

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	14	46.67%
Proficient	85 – 89	13	43.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	3	10.00%
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	89.00	Proficient	

The learners in this group's performance can be considered adequate knowledge of grammatical rules. Furthermore, they have become acquainted with the grammar structure covered in the test. It can be concluded that the learners' grammar competency has improved because of the SAMR model.

To support this claim, Sosas (2021), cited that the internet, podcasts, video conferencing, videos, and some of the best instruments for training speaking skills include speech recognition software, TELL, and blogging. It claimed that technology was used for instructional speech rather than in trades and economic activities. It became the way of communication for instructors and students nowadays, which meant that technology was required to enter the modernized world. Technology became an additional tool for teachers to improve the student's speaking abilities.

Table 5.2. B. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Grammar

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	8	26.67%
Proficient	85 – 89	10	33.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	12	40.00%
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	86.07	Proficient	

The use of technology or gamification is critical in providing language learners with a quality learning experience. The results show how this approach affects the writing skills of the students in terms of grammar.

Tran and Nguyen (2021) claimed that digital games were useful to improve learners' grammar in aspects concerning the use of modals, gerunds, and infinitives; also, students showed an improvement in their vocabulary knowledge, especially in topics related to jobs and education.

Table 5.3. A. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	13	43.33%
Proficient	85 – 89	5	16.67%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	12	40.00%
Developing	75 – 79	0	0

Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	87.07	Proficient	

This means that the students are well-directed to complete learning tasks for them to develop as effective participants they gain self-confidence and competency in the use of the English language, resulting in good communication skills. They are encouraged to use new technology platforms to share their ideas and opinions.

In addition, Mahdi (2022) claimed that the effect of digital news on spoken language skills and the development of content knowledge to the 15 students who used Voice Thread, an interactive media tool had a good impact on student's speaking skill development. The strategy empowered the learners and resulted in improved communication among them. It also improved students' speaking fluency.

Table 5.3. B. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Fluency

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	3	10.00%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	24	80.00%
Developing	75 – 79	3	10.00%
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	81.93	Approaching Proficient	

This simply implies that the students are correctly guided to complete the writing tasks for them to develop as fluent writers. They gain self-confidence and proficiency in the use of the English language, resulting in good communication skills. They are encouraged to use new technological platforms such as digital portfolios to focus on art, pronunciation, and fluency.

According to Cabrera-Solano (2020), the results demonstrated that the digital portfolios were beneficial in improving students' pronunciation and fluency. It was also confirmed that using Google Drive to create digital portfolios could boost students' motivation to improve speaking skills in the target language.

Table 5.4. A. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Speaking) in terms of Word Choice

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	14	46.67%
Proficient	85 – 89	13	43.33%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	3	10.00%
Developing	75 – 79	0	0
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	89.27	Proficient	

The result simply means that the students have enhanced their vocabulary. The results also indicated that the student's ability to select the appropriate term in each topic had improved. Learners can benefit from technology-mediated learning, such as video conferencing, to improve their vocabulary through collaborative learning.

Lenkaitis (2020) revealed that technology-mediated learning occurred because participants were collaborative learners who communicated with other members of the group. Video conferencing like Zoom enhanced the improvement of conversation skills by allowing learners to contribute individually to the conversation to 'build confidence... with a safe setting in which to practice and assess themselves.

Table 5.4. B. Posttest Result of the Tourism Students in the Experimental Group in English Language Proficiency (Writing) in terms of Word Choice

Indicators	Grade	F	%
Advanced	90 – 100	0	0
Proficient	85 – 89	5	16.67%
Approaching Proficient	80 – 84	24	80.00%
Developing	75 – 79	1	3.33%
Beginning	74 and below	0	0
Total		30	100%
General Assessment	82.80	Approaching Proficient	

The results show that their written expression performance has improved. It is possible to conclude that the students in this group no longer have difficulty with word choice in the written and can already explain cohesive concepts. It means that the teacher's use of the interactive tool "Grammarly" in class aided students in enhancing their written expression.

In support of this, according to the study by Koltovskaia (2020), Grammarly was recommended for students with low levels of English competence for them to receive sufficient direction and training on how to effectively engage in writing with the assistance of Grammarly feedback.

Table 6.1. Test of Significant Difference between the English Language Proficiency Posttest Scores in Speaking of Tourism Students in Control and the Experimental Group

Pretest	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	p value		
Organization	-1.05333	.78597	-7.340	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Grammar	-1.28000	.69798	-10.045	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Fluency	-1.04667	.62958	-9.106	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Word Choice	-1.30667	.66795	-10.715	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

This suggests that the experimental and control groups obtained different outcomes. Another implication is that after exposing the Experimental group to the SAMR model during their session, they display near mastery.

Wahyuni et al. (2020) concluded that the usage of technology may broaden student's knowledge and skills in the language. Furthermore, incorporating technology may help learners to be more creative and self-directed learners.

Table 6.2. Test of Significant Difference between the English Language Proficiency Posttest Scores in Writing of Tourism Students in Control and the Experimental Group

Pretest	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	p value		
Organization	-1.16667	.52806	-12.101	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Grammar	-.81333	.40999	-10.866	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Fluency	-.71333	.39543	-9.881	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Word Choice	-.84000	.27493	-16.735	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

It signifies that the experimental and control groups got different results. Another result is that after exposing the Experimental group to the SAMR paradigm during their online course, they displayed nearly mastery level.

Indonesia's (2019) findings were validated in the study The Use of Integrated Technology of Substitution, Augmentation, Modification and Redefinition in Increasing

English Skill at Stik Siti Khadijah Palembang. Using information technology made learning English more enjoyable, SAMR models could boost students' capacity to learn English, particularly writing abilities, and the usage of SAMR models in learning makes English courses more fascinating. The use of SAMR models could promote student creativity in the use of information technology, making learning English more genuine, and students feel the benefits of adopting the SAMR model. Students preferred to learn English independently through online media, with 96.7% stating that they preferred to learn English with online facilities.

Conclusions

Based on the abovementioned findings of the study, the following conclusions have been obtained:

1. That Tourism students in the control group do not know enough about grammatical rules and are unfamiliar with their structure during their pretest. On the other side, the students have difficulties in writing and speaking in English and cannot explain cohesive thoughts. Furthermore, the students are reported to be inadequate in terms of organization. They are unable to understand the content and lack language of proficiency.
2. That during their pretest for speaking and writing competencies, students in the experimental group performed poorly in grammar. The pupils are unable to express coherent ideas and do not know enough grammar rules. Still, there is room for improvement in the learner's organizing skills for both competencies. Conversely, the students have trouble with word choice and fluency. Their poor language skills prevent them from understanding what they are reading.
3. That as the results of their pretests are nearly identical, the control and experimental groups perform similarly at the start of the research. The pretest results for both speaking and writing skills do not reveal any statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups, indicating that previous to the design and implementation of the study, all groups were at or near identical levels of English language competency.
4. That the Tourism students in the control group are unfamiliar with the structure of grammar throughout their posttest in terms of speaking and writing skills. Similarly, there is a bit of improvement in their written expression performance. Furthermore, the student's fluency skills are poor.
5. That the Tourism students in the experimental group demonstrated a sufficient grasp of grammatical rules throughout their posttest. Furthermore, they are now familiar with the grammatical structure that will be tested. One may claim that the instructor's use of

SAMR in the classroom improved the students' grammar proficiency. Similarly, their ability in organization and fluency has improved.

6. That the control and experimental groups perform differently after the posttest because their posttest results differ. The posttest findings of the experimental and control groups demonstrate a substantial difference. Based on the implementation and deployment of the SAMR model to the experimental, one may deduce that performance changes.

7. As a result of this study, "WRITE2SPEAK" an action plan was proposed to help the learners deal with the areas in which they are having difficulty, like organization, grammar, fluency, and word choice.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are strongly encouraged considering the findings and conclusions:

1. The learners may be given the most relevant instructions in subject-verb agreement and basic essay writing to assist them in becoming more adept in grammar as quickly as possible. Additionally, learners may broaden their vocabulary range, avoid recurrent errors in word choice, and avoid confusing words that are irrelevant to the topic. This set of students, on the other hand, requires a more significant amount of reading resources to be better equipped in terms of organizing and gathering ideas.

2. The learners may be introduced to fundamental sentence construction and grammar standards. To help with the expression of cogent ideas, they may also increase the scope of their vocabulary. Yet, the learner's speaking and writing abilities still need to be developed and improved. In addition to these topics, they may learn about capitalization, punctuation, spelling, pronunciation, articulation, handwriting, vocabulary, word usage, sentence structure, and paragraph organization. On the other hand, learners need more appropriate reading materials to enhance their language understanding.

3. Before the design and implementation of the study, the control and experimental groups have the same degree of English language competency for both competencies since they performed similarly at the beginning of the investigation and showed almost no variations in their pretest scores. Therefore, students can enhance their organization, grammar, fluency, and word choice by following the first two criteria mentioned above.

4. Instructors may use the SAMR model in their instruction to help students become more proficient in speaking and writing English by considering the posttest results of the tourism students in the control group.

5. Teachers can keep using the SAMR approach in their instruction to help students practice and get better at speaking and writing English, considering the posttest outcomes of the tourism students in the experimental group.

6. It is suggested to continue using this strategy in teaching because there is a substantial difference in the outcome of the control and experimental groups following the execution and implementation of the SAMR model in the experimental group.

7. This study's suggested outcome, an action plan called "WRITE2SPEAK," is currently advised for approval. It can be used to help students deal with areas where they are having difficulty, like organization, grammar, fluency, and word choice.

8. The results of this study may be used by future researchers in their work helping all learners improve their speaking and writing proficiency in the English language. They would refer to and use pertinent studies and literature as a resource.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research study followed ethical guidelines. Since these ethical problems were explored throughout this work, the study adhered to the ethical guidelines outlined in the research manual published by the institution. To ensure that the participants understood that their remarks and opinions would be kept private and that this study would not hurt them, the researcher wrote a consent letter outlining the guidelines and goal of the study. The research study was kept confidential the entire time, and in the research content letter, the researcher would use the proper name of the study. For the public to trust and support the study, the researcher adhered to ethical standards. The expert ensured that the respondents' data was protected. Additionally, the purpose of the questionnaire was to collect only the data required for this study; respondents were not asked any private or sensitive questions, and the names of the students were not published in the report in response to the Data Privacy Act of the Philippines 2012, also known as Republic Act No. 10173.

Acknowledgments

To begin, the researcher wishes to express his gratitude to his thesis adviser, Dr. Vivien E. Untalan, for being always available to assist him anytime he encounters a problem or query regarding his research.

Furthermore, the researcher wishes to express gratitude to the following:

A heartfelt thanks to Dr. Ma. Lorena Tagala, the Research Director of LCBA, for her tireless efforts. Without her guidance, this study would not have been possible;

Moreover, the researcher would like to acknowledge Dr. Peejay G. Gecolea and Dean Alfredo G. Perez Jr. of the School of Graduate Studies. The researcher wants to extend his gratitude for their insightful comments on this thesis. Additionally, the researcher

wishes to thank the very approachable Dr. Melchor Villapando, for serving as the study's statistician;

The researcher would like to express his heartfelt appreciation to his Papa Remy and Mama Rose for their unwavering support and encouragement during his years of study and the process of researching and writing this thesis. Without them, this feat would not have been possible, and to his beloved Ms. Joella Nolasco for her unending support and love;

Finally, Thanks to our Lord Jesus Christ, to Him be glory forever!

REFERENCES

- Ambarwati, R., & Mandasari, B. (2020). The Influence Of Online Cambridge Dictionary Toward Students' Pronunciation And Vocabulary Mastery. *Journal Of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 1(2), 50-55.
- Asio, H., & Quijano, M. G. (2023). English Proficiency And Academic Performance Of College Students. *International Journal Of Multidisciplinary Research And Analysis*, 06(03). <https://Doi.Org/10.47191/Ijmra/V6-I3-50>
- Aziz, A. A., & Kashinathan, S. (2021). ESL Learners' Challenges In Speaking English In Malaysian Classroom. *Development*, 10(2), 983-991.
- Betoni, T., & Ulfaika, R. (2020). The Correlation Between Students' Grammatical Mastery and Students' Writing Achievement At Xi Grade Students Of Sman 1 Tarakan Academic Year 2019/2020. *Borneo Journal Of English Language Education*, 2(1).
- Budiharto, R. A. (2019). Native Language Interference on Target Language Writings Of Indonesian EFL Students: An Exploratory Case Study. *Indonesian EFL Journal*, 5(1), 107-116.
- Cabrera-Solano, P. (2020). The use of digital portfolios to enhance english as a foreign language speaking skills in higher education. *International Journal Of Emerging Technologies In Learning (Ijet)*, 15(24), 159-175.
- Derakhshan, A., & Karimian Shirejini, R. (2020). An Investigation of The Iranian EFL Learners' Perceptions Towards The Most Common Writing Problems. *Sage Open*, 10(2), 2158244020919523.
- Eisenberg, S. L. (2020). Using General Language Performance Measures to Assess Grammar Learning. *Topics In Language Disorders*, 40(2), 135-148.
- Farhan, W., Razmak, J., Demers, S., & Laflamme, S. (2019). E-Learning Systems Versus Instructional Communication Tools: Developing and Testing a New E-Learning User Interface from The Perspectives of Teachers And Students. *Technology In Society*, 59, 101192.
- Fitria, T. N. (2021). Grammarly As AI-Powered English Writing Assistant: Students' Alternative for Writing English. *Metathesis: Journal Of English Language, Literature, And Teaching*, 5(1), 65-78.
- Indonesia, A. B. A. B. I. (2019). The Use Of Integrated Technology Of Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, And Redefinition In Increasing English Skill At Stik Siti Khadijah Palembang. 16 November 2019, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia
- Islam, M. S., & Stapa, M. B. (2021). Students' Low Proficiency In Spoken English In Private Universities In Bangladesh: Reasons And Remedies. *Language Testing In Asia*, 11, 1-31.

- Izza, A., & Rusydiyah, E. F. (2020). Analisis Model SAM/R Pada Guru Pendidikan Agama Islam Dalam Mengembangkan Motivasi Belajar Siswa. *Edureligia: Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 4(1), 11-34.
- Koltovskaia, S. (2020). Student Engagement with Automated Written Corrective Feedback (AWCF) Provided By Grammarly: A Multiple Case Study. *Assessing Writing*, 44, 100450.
- Lenkaitis, C. A. (2020). Technology as a Mediating Tool: Videoconferencing, L2 Learning, And Learner Autonomy. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 33(5-6), 483-509.
- Limpo, T., & Graham, S. (2019). The Role of Handwriting Instruction In Writers' Education. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 68(3), 311–329.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00071005.2019.1692127>
- Mahdi, D. A. (2022). Improving Speaking and Presentation Skills Through Interactive Multimedia Environment For Non-Native Speakers Of English. *SAGE Open*, 12(1), 21582440221079811.
- Mandasari, B., & Aminatun, D. (2020). VLOG: A Tool to Improve Students' English Speaking Ability At University Level. *Proceedings Universitas Pamulang*, 1(1).
- Mantra, I. B. N., Handayani, N. D., & Widiastuti, I. A. M. S. (2021). Empowering Mind Mapping Strategy to Improve Students' Writing Skills In The EFL Classroom. *International Journal Of Linguistics And Discourse Analytics*, 3(1), 14-21.
- Mariñas, J. (2021, July 28). 3 Reasons Why the Philippines is One of the Top English-Proficient Countries for Business. *Cloud Employee*.
- Masuram, J., & Sripada, P. N. (2020). Developing Spoken Fluency Through Task-Based Teaching. *Procedia Computer Science*, 172, 623-630.
- Namaziandost, E., Homayouni, M., & Rahmani, P. (2020). The impact of cooperative learning approach on the development of efl learners' speaking Fluency. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 7(1), 1780811.
- Omar, Y. Z. (2019). Teaching Pedagogical Grammar in Context To Enrich English Language Learners' Academic Writing. *Online Submission*, 2(3), 213-225.
- Papageorgiou, S., Davis, L., Norris, J. M., Garcia Gomez, P., Manna, V. F., & Monfils, L. (2021). Design Framework for The TOEFL Essentials Test 2021. *Research Memorandum No. RM-21-03*. ETS. <https://www.ets.org/media/research/pdf/RM-21-03.pdf>.
- Pham, V. P. H. (2021). The Effects Of Collaborative Writing On Students' Writing Fluency: An Efficient Framework For Collaborative Writing. *Sage Open*, 11(1), 2158244021998363.
- Puspitaloka, N. (2019). The Effects of Grammar Mastery and Critical Thinking Towards Student's Descriptive Writing Skill. *ELT In Focus*, 2(1), 19-28.
- Ramamuthie, V., & Aziz, A. A. (2022). Systematic Review: The Effectiveness Of Digital Tools To Improve Writing Skill Of ESL Students. *International Journal Of Academic In Business And Social Science*, 12(3), 408-427.
- Retnaningsih, R. (2020). E-Learning System Sebuah Solusi Pragmatis Program Vokasional Semasa Pandemi COVID19. *Jurnal Taman Vokasi*, 8(1), 28–34.
<https://doi.org/10.30738/Jtv.V8i1.7751>
- Siddiqui, K. A. (2020). Analyzing Factors Influencing the Paragraph Organization In English Language Writing Of Intermediate Students. *International Journal Of Teaching And Learning In Higher Education*, 32(1), 99-106.
- Sosas, R. V. (2021). Technology In Teaching Speaking and Its Effects To Students Learning English. *Journal Of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 17(2), 958-970.
- Speck, B. G. (2022). Students' Perceptions of Online Equine Courses and Their Impacts on Learning Outcomes.
- Su, Y. C. (2021). College Students' Oral Communication Strategy Use, Self-Perceived English Proficiency and Confidence, And Communication Anxiety In Taiwan's EFL Learning. *Educational Studies*, 57(6), 650-669.

- Syafiq, A. N., Rahmawati, A., Anwari, A., & Oktaviana, T. (2021). Increasing Speaking Skill Through Youtube Video as English Learning Material During Online Learning In Pandemic COVID-19. *Elsya: Journal Of English Language Studies*, 3, 50- 55. <https://doi.org/10.31849/Elsya.V3i1.6206>
- Tavakoli, P., Nakatsuhara, F., & Hunter, A. M. (2020). Aspects Of Fluency Across Assessed Levels Of Speaking Proficiency. *The Modern Language Journal*, 104(1), 169-191.
- Thomas, L. (2020). An Introduction To Quasi-Experimental Designs. Scribbr. Retrieved From: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quasi-experimental-design/>
- Toba, R., & Noor, W. N. (2019). The Current Issues of Indonesian EFL Students' Writing Skills: Ability, Problem, And Reason In Writing Comparison And Contrast Essay. *Dinamika Ilmu*, 19(1), 57-73.
- Tran, T. M. L., & Nguyen, T. T. H. (2021). The Impacts of Technology-Based Communication on EFL Students' Writing. *Asiacall Online Journal*, 12(5), 54-76.
- Wahyuni, S., Mujiyanto, J., Rukmini, D., & Fitriati, S. W. (2020, June). Teachers' Technology Integration into English Instructions: SAMR Model. In *International Conference on Science and Education And Technology (ISET 2019)* (Pp. 546-550). Atlantis Press.
- Wahyuningsih, S., & Afandi, M. (2020). Investigating English Speaking Problems: Implications for Speaking Curriculum Development In Indonesia. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 9(3), 967-977.
- Waluyo, B., & Bucol, J. L. (2021). The Impact of Gamified Vocabulary Learning Using Quizlet On Low-Proficiency Students. *Computer-Assisted Language Learning*, 22(1), 158-179.
- Williams, C., & Beam, S. (2019). Technology And Writing: Review Of Research. *Computers & Education*, 128, 227-242.
- Zohrabi, M., & Tahmasebi, Z. (2020). A Study of The Effect of Dictogloss as a Medium Of Form-Focused Instruction On Vocabulary Versus Grammar Development Of Iranian EFL Learners. *Applied Research on English Language*, 9(2), 183-204.
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